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Suy Suy Kan Apuh Dagan *A Tale from Tausug Literature*

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Long ago, there lived a devoted married couple, Sumagsag and Ahadiya, (not their real names) bound by love and faith. Though their days were filled with happiness, their hearts longed for one precious blessing—a child. Accordingly, they lived in a place known Tuyang in Talipao, Sulu. They lived a happy and peaceful life near a creek and close to the sea. After several years of waiting to have a child, the wife finally became pregnant, and the couple was extremely happy and excited, along with their relatives, for the arrival of the baby. While praying, the family is over the moon with gratitude to Almighty God because Ahadiya did not have difficulty during childbirth, the beautiful baby girl delivered quickly from her womb; however, the family were struck with astonishment when the Panday, a Tausug traditional midwife declared that the children were twins. “Subhānallāh,” the midwife exclaimed. “This is Allah’s will.” She added, the babies were two: one a healthy baby girl, and the other a crocodile.”

Despite this unusual situation, and the different reactions from the community, the couple remain strong and grateful for the blessings that Allah had granted them. On the day of aqeeqa celebration of the Muslims, when the child is formally given a name, the couple remained happy and their children were finally named Rahma (not her real name) for the baby girl while the baby crocodile named Apuh Dagan. The couple tried to live normally with equal treatment to their children and provides all the needs of the two. That’s why the twins grew up together and happy as if nothing could separate them. They play, eat together and agree with each other in all things.

All of a sudden, the joyful home was shadowed by sorrow, for two souls born of the same womb were forced to part because of the unstoppable continuous growth of the male crocodile Apuh Dagan, he can no longer possible to live at home. The time has come that it is necessary for the twins to live separately. One day, filled with sadness and crying heavily from the weight of their hearts, the couple decided to separate the twins. Rahma would remain with their parents, while Apuh Dagan would live in the water near the sea, where he truly belonged.

The next day, the family took Dagan to where he should live. Several days passed though, she had been told not to, Rahma could not bear to stay away from her sibling. She visited, and once more, joy filled their hearts as they were together and when their parents discovered that they were still meeting, they became angry and almost never allowed her to get close to her crocodile brother for her safety even if Apuh Dagan is different and did not attack human, as crocodiles are known to be potentially dangerous animals. They are apex predators and have been known to attack humans if they feel threatened or if they are hungry.

As an obedient child, Rahma promised to never see her brother again. But the twins love and care for each other very much. So, the two were still meeting secretly and whenever the two are together they are both happy, there were times when the crocodile takes her sister to his journey to other places and enjoy. One afternoon, Rahma was very excited to visit her sibling, bringing along his favorite roasted chicken, but she found her brother covered in blood and she learned that he had been fighting other crocodiles in order to survive. "Rahma said angrily, 'May all the evil creatures that bit you and caused you suffering die. I will treat your wounds so you can be strong again, and we will fight them". She immediately cure the wounded brother and as soon as her brother recovered, she decided to support her brother in his battles by feeding him more foods to become stronger and sharpening his teeth using her father's whetstone, so that his teeth would be sharp and he could win in his fight. It was not long before the crocodile fought again and successfully defeated all his opponents. From then on, he kept winning battle after battle, and his sister also felt happy every time he won.

As years passed by, despite his strength and his successful fights against other crocodiles, the time came when he grew old and his body weakened. There were battles in which he suffered many wounds and became frail. On the other hand, Rahma became busy as she had already started her own family, she could hardly visit her crocodile brother anymore.

Suddenly, Apuh Dagan got sick and his illness worsened day by day while longing for his sister and this led to his death. When Rahma learned of her brother's death, she immediately went to the place where he used to live. There she saw her crocodile brother's body lying. She nearly fainted as she cried, blaming herself for not visiting him for so long. "Forgive me! Forgive me! I know you must have thought of me while you were struggling," she shouted while hugging her crocodile brother's body. Rahma, was wrapped in sorrow deep, for the crocodile sibling he could no longer keep. She wept for days, her heart in regret, wishing she had visited, a bond not to forget. It did not take long before she learned to accept her sibling's fate. Coming from a strong and God-fearing family, in Islam, being God-fearing also means believing that all events, whether sorrowful or even death, should be accepted, for they are part of God's will. So, she continued her life, but the memories of his brother still remain in his heart and mind.

Here the story of Apuh Dagan, comes to an end, its truth still uncertain whether fact or fiction passed down through generations from the elders to the present day. However, the writer gladly shared the tale in order to preserve a story passed down from the ancestors of his mother's family from Tuyang, Sulu. Nevertheless, she relates that even up to the present time, there are still people who believe that whenever there is a crocodile that does not bite humans, it is said to have come from the lineage of Apuh Dagan.